

Supplementary Table S3. Sequence analysis and model selection for datasets used in phylogenetic analyses and ancestral state reconstructions via (a) BEAST and (b) IQ-TREE.

Supplementary Table S3a. Sequence analysis and model selection for molecular datasets used in simultaneous Bayesian analysis via BEAST, with gene, original sequence length, sequence length after removal of ambiguously aligned regions by Gblocks; alignment of COI was unambiguous (NA). Sequence analysis was performed via IQ-TREE (variable sites, phylogenetically informative sites). The best nucleotide substitution models were determined by ModelTest-NG using the Akaike Information Criterion (score given); where the best model was not available in BEAST, the model with the next best score was selected.

Gene	Original sequence length (bp)	Sequence length after Gblocks (% of original length) (bp)	Variable sites (bp)	Phylogenetically informative sites (bp)	Best model under AICc	Score
COI	658	NA	268	257	TrN93+I+G	20538.6528
12S	640	542 (85%)	274	227	HKY+I+G	13028.5093
16S	554	497 (90%)	178	164	HKY+I+G	9704.0321
28S	1630	1363 (84%)	337	220	GTR+I+G	10551.1617

Supplementary Table S3b. Sequence analysis and model selection for molecular datasets used in Maximum Likelihood analysis of mitogenome and/or nuclear data via IQ-TREE, with gene, original sequence length, sequence length after removal of ambiguously aligned regions by Gblocks. Sequence analysis was performed via IQ-TREE (variable sites, phylogenetically informative sites). The best nucleotide substitution models were determined by ModelTest-NG using the Akaike Information Criterion (score given).

Gene	Original sequence length (bp)	Sequence length after Gblocks (% of original length) (bp)	Variable sites (bp)	Phylogenetically informative sites (bp)	Best model under AICc	Score
ATP6	696	695	355	284	TVM+I+G4	12442.7019
ATP8	159	NA	70	79	TVM+I+G4	3102.4097

COI	1536	NA	957	517	TIM+I+G4	22926.0585
COII	687	NA	413	236	GTR+I+G4	10282.9674
COIII	780	NA	440	295	GTR+I+G4	13086.4578
CYTB	1140	NA	605	458	GTR+I+G4	19996.6742
ND1	942	941	477	394	TVM+I+G4	16927.6003
ND2	1065	1057	360	593	GTR+I+G4	24518.8645
ND3	354	353	165	156	GTR+I+G4	6627.3637
ND4	1374	1373	559	703	GTR+I+G4	29497.5189
ND4L	297	NA	134	134	TPM2u+I+G4	5694.9567
ND5	1760	1715	747	836	TVM+I+G4	36539.4513
ND6	522	494	165	265	TVM+I+G4	11370.4217
12S	968	816	425	279	TIM2+I+G4	11524.5871
16S	1540	1117	603	379	TIM2+I+G4	16351.6402
18S	1940	1823	1678	90	TIM3+G4	10106.5641
28S	1563	1239	1055	105	TIM+I+G4	7066.6220